

1 rasterdiv - an Information Theory tailored
2 R package for measuring ecosystem
3 heterogeneity from space: to the origin and
4 back

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Abstract

69
70 1. Ecosystem heterogeneity has been widely recognized as a key
71 ecological feature, influencing several ecological functions, since it is
72 strictly related to several ecological functions like diversity patterns
73 and change, metapopulation dynamics, population connectivity, or
74 gene flow.

75
76 2. In this paper, we present a new R package - `rasterdiv` - to cal-
77 culate heterogeneity indices based on remotely sensed data. We also
78 provide an ecological application at the landscape scale and demon-
79 strate its power in revealing potentially hidden heterogeneity patterns.

80
81 3. The `rasterdiv` package allows calculating multiple indices de-
82 rived from remote sensing, robustly rooted in Information Theory, and
83 based on reproducible open source algorithms.

84 *Keywords:* biodiversity; ecological informatics; modeling; remote sensing;
85 satellite imagery.

86 *'I'll be back'* (A. Schwarzenegger, *The Terminator*, 1984)

87 **1 Introduction**

88 Ecosystem heterogeneity drives a number of ecological processes and func-
89 tions such as species diversity patterns and change (Rocchini et al., 2018),
90 metapopulation dynamics (Fahrig, 2007), population connectivity (Malan-
91 son and Cramer, 1999) or gene flow (Lozier et al., 2013). Heterogeneity has
92 been defined in various ways in the scientific literature: (i) as the variation
93 in space and time of qualitative and quantitative descriptors of an environ-
94 mental variable of interest (Li and Reynolds, 1995); (ii) as the horizontal
95 component of habitat variation (August, 1983; Grelle, 2003); (iii) as the spa-
96 tially structured variability of the habitat (Ettema et al., 2002); or (iv) as
97 within-habitat variability (Heaney, 2001; Hortal et al., 2009). In this paper,
98 it will be considered as an umbrella concept representing the degree of non-
99 uniformity in land cover, vegetation and physical factors (topography, soil,
100 topoclimate and microclimate, Stein et al., 2014).

101 Landscape heterogeneity across different spatial extents and over differ-
102 ent temporal periods can be inferred by applying algorithms based on remote
103 sensing and spatial ecology (Skidmore et al., 2011; Schimel and Scheiner,
104 2019). Remotely sensed spectral heterogeneity measures of a landscape rep-
105 resent a valid alternative to categorical land cover maps, which, especially
106 in the case of non-homogeneous and complex landscape configurations (e.g.
107 mosaic of crops and semi-natural forests), might suffer from oversimplifica-
108 tion when investigated through land cover classes (Rocchini et al., 2019; Da
109 Re et al., 2019). Heterogeneous landscapes should present higher spectral
110 heterogeneity values compared to more homogeneous landscapes within the
111 same spatial extent (Rocchini and Ricotta, 2007). It follows that remotely
112 sensed spectral heterogeneity can be profitably used to measure landscape
113 heterogeneity in space and time in order to convey information on ecosystem
114 processes and functioning (Schneider et al., 2017).

115 From this point of view, the development of Free and Open Source algo-
116 rithms to measure and monitor (i.e. repeated measures over time) landscape
117 or ecosystem heterogeneity from space would allow robust, reproducible and
118 standardized estimates of ecosystem functioning and services (Rocchini and
119 Neteler, 2012). Furthermore, their intrinsic transparency, community-vetoing
120 options, sharing and rapid availability are also valuable additions and rea-
121 sons to move towards open source options. Among the different open source
122 software options, the R software is certainly one of the most used statisti-
123 cal and computational environment worldwide and different packages have

124 already been devoted to remote sensing data processing for: (i) raster data
125 management (`raster` package, Hijmans and van Etten (2020)); (ii) remote
126 sensing data analysis (`RStoolbox` package, Leutner et al. (2019)); (iii) spec-
127 tral species diversity (`biodivMapR` package, Féret and Boissieu (2020)); (iv)
128 Sparse Generalized Dissimilarity Modelling based on remote sensing data
129 (`sgdm` package, Leitao et al. (2017)); (v) entropy-based local spatial associa-
130 tion (`ELSA` package, Naimi et al. (2019)); or (vi) landscape metrics calcula-
131 tion (`landscapemetrics` package, Hesselbarth et al. (2019)), to name just a
132 few. Readers can also refer to [https://cran.r-project.org/web/views/
133 Spatial.html](https://cran.r-project.org/web/views/Spatial.html) for the CRAN Task View on analysis of spatial data.

134 Nonetheless, currently no R package provides a flow of functions grounded
135 in Information Theory and generalized entropy, incorporating abundance in-
136 formation for each informative value but also the relative numerical distance
137 among the said values. In this paper we introduce the new `rasterdiv` R pack-
138 age, now available under the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN,
139 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv>), which provides such
140 a set of functions' throughput workflow. The aim of this manuscript is to
141 briefly introduce the theory under the `rasterdiv` package and to provide an
142 ecological example demonstrating its ability to measure several aspects of
143 landscape or ecosystem heterogeneity.

144 **2 Brief description of the theoretical frame- 145 work on information theory based metrics**

146 **2.1 Shannon entropy**

147 Shannon's theory (Shannon, 1948), profoundly rooted in Eduard Boltzmann
148 (Boltzmann, 1872) studies, is a solid basis for calculating landscape hetero-
149 geneity and it has been widely used in several ecological applications (refer
150 to Vranken et al., 2014 for a review).

151 Given a sample area with N pixel values and p_i relative abundances for
152 every $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, in decreasing order, the Shannon index is calculated
153 as:

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \ln p_i \quad (1)$$

154 When applying such indices to remotely sensed data, the image is divided
155 into small chunks of the whole image, commonly defined as 'kernels', 'win-
156 dows' or 'moving windows' (Box 1). These terms will be used throughout
157 this manuscript to relay the local scale of analysis.

158 In the Shannon index the relative abundance of pixel values (e.g. re-
159 flectance values, vegetation indices) is considered. The higher the richness
160 and turnover, the higher will be the equitability of values and thus the Shan-
161 non index.

162 2.2 Rényi generalized entropy

163 Any point descriptor of information heterogeneity, like the previously cited
164 Shannon's H is not able to describe the whole potential spectrum of hetero-
165 geneity as it usually measures only one part or component of heterogeneity
166 (e.g. richness, evenness, nestedness, etc.). Hence, no single measure can be
167 used to represent such a wide spectrum (Gorelick, 2011a; Nakamura et al.,
168 2020).

169 Rényi (1970) proposed a method to generalize entropy measurements in
170 just one formula, changing one parameter, called *alpha* in its original formu-
171 lation.

172 Given a sample area with N pixel values and p_i relative abundances for
173 every $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, the Rényi entropy index is:

$$H_\alpha = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \times \ln \sum_{i=1}^N p_i^\alpha \quad (2)$$

174 Changing the parameter α will lead to different indices starting from
175 the same formula (Hill, 1973). As an example, when $\alpha=0$, $H_0 = \ln(N)$
176 where N =richness, namely the maximum possible Shannon index (H_{max}).
177 In practice, with $\alpha = 0$, all the spectral values equally contribute to the
178 index, without making use of their relative abundance. For $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, the
179 Rényi entropy index will equal Shannon H , according to the l'Hôpital's rule
180 (a mathematical proof is provided in Appendix 1), while for $\alpha=2$ the Rényi
181 entropy index will equal the $\ln(1/D)$ where D is the Simpson's dominance
182 (Simpson, 1949). The theoretical curve relating the Rényi entropy index
183 and α is a negative exponential, i.e. it decays until flattening for higher
184 values of α , where the weight of the most abundant spectral values is higher
185 with small differences among the attained heterogeneity maps (Ricotta et al.
186 (2003a)). Besides the Rényi's generalized entropy, the `rasterdiv` package
187 includes generalized metrics as the Hill's numbers (Hill, 1973).

188 2.3 Rao's Q heterogeneity index

189 The previously described metrics have no dimension. In other words, they
190 do not consider the relative difference among pixel values but just the pres-

191 ence of a different class. For example, having $A = (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9)$ and
 192 $B = (1, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5, 10^6, 10^7, 10^8, 10^9)$ as two theoretical arrays contain-
 193 ing values that are different from each other, the Shannon index will always
 194 be maximum, i.e. $H = \log(9) = 2.197225$, despite the relative numerical
 195 distance between pairs of values.

196 In remote sensing this is a critical point since contiguous zones of a satel-
 197 lite image might have similar (but not strictly equal) reflectance values. For
 198 instance, the variability of a homogeneous surface, e.g., a woodland patch or
 199 a water area, would be overestimated if spectral distances among values are
 200 not considered in the calculation.

201 The Rao's Quadratic heterogeneity measure (hereafter Rao's Q , Rao
 202 (1982)) can be applied to overcome this issue, considering both relative abun-
 203 dances and spectral distances among pixel values in the calculation.

204 Given the values of different pixels i and j , the Rao's Q considers their
 205 pairwise distance d_{ij} as:

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N d_{ij} \times p_i \times p_j \quad (3)$$

206 Accordingly, an array with different but spectrally near values will convey
 207 a high Shannon's H but a low Rao's Q . Conversely, an array with different
 208 and distant spectral values will convey both a high Shannon's H and a high
 209 Rao's Q .

210 Given a 3x3 pixels matrix M : $M = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & \lambda_2 & \lambda_3 \\ \lambda_4 & \lambda_5 & \lambda_6 \\ \lambda_7 & \lambda_8 & \lambda_9 \end{pmatrix}$ where λ is the re-
 211 flectance value for every pixel in a single 8-bit band (256 possible values), a
 212 pairwise distance matrix M_d is derived for all pixel values:

$$M_d = \begin{pmatrix} d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_n} \\ d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_n} \\ d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

213 Then, according to Equation 3, Rao's Q is obtained as the sum of every
 214 pairwise distance multiplied by the relative abundances of all the pairs of
 215 pixels in the analyzed image $d \times (1/N^2)$. Strictly speaking, Rao's Q can be
 216 defined as the expected difference in reflectance values between two pixels
 217 drawn randomly with replacement from the evaluated set of pixels.

218 It is possible to construct the distance matrix for several dimensions (lay-
219 ers) in order to consider multiple bands at a time and calculate Rao's Q in
220 a multidimensional (multi-layers) system.

221 To illustrate the benefit of the functions provided in the `rasterdiv` pack-
222 age, we propose to apply it on an ecological study case in the following
223 section.

224 **3 Application: the ecosystem heterogeneity** 225 **of the Ötzi area**

226 In order to show the capabilities of the `rasterdiv` package, we decided to
227 focus on one of the geologically and biologically most diverse mountain re-
228 gions worldwide: the Similaun and Ortles glaciers in Italy. This region is
229 not only important for its rich geobiodiversity but also for its fascinating
230 archeological history, also due to an incredible anthropological discovery of
231 the early nineties: the famous Ötzi Tyrolean iceman (Keller et al., 2012).
232 The study area we are focusing on for applying the `rasterdiv` package is
233 included between the Ortles and the Similaun glaciers, in the Alps of north-
234 ern Italy (Figure 1). Below, we provide a step by step tutorial which can
235 be reproduced for any area and by every researcher worldwide. The only
236 required input data are satellite images.

237 We used Copernicus Sentinel-2 data at a spatial resolution of 10 m (Figure
238 1) acquired on May 9th 2020. Once the satellite image was downloaded from
239 the Copernicus Open Access Hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>), we
240 computed NDVI and rescaled it at an 8-bit radiometric resolution. Hence,
241 NDVI values were used as the input information (values) to compute the
242 ecosystem heterogeneity indices described in the former section. More specif-
243 ically, based on the NDVI raster grid used as input object, we ran a set of
244 functions provided in the `rasterdiv` package and written in Box 2.

Box 2 - Code used under rasterdiv

```
## Shannon's H 1
sha <- Shannon(ndvi_8bit, window = 9, na.tolerance = 0.9,
  np = 3)
# where: ndvi_8bit = input data, window = moving window 3
# size, na.tolerance = proportion of tolerated NA values,
# np = number of processes (cores)

## Renyi entropy 5
ren <- Renyi(ndvi_8bit, window = 9, alpha = seq(0,10), na.
  tolerance = 0.9, np = 3, cluster.type = "SOCK")
# where: alpha = alpha value in the Renyi formula (in this 7
# case all integer alpha values from 0 to 10)

## Rao's Q 9
rao <- Rao(ndvi_8bit, window = 9, na.tolerance = 0.9, dist_
  m = "euclidean", np = 3, cluster.type = "SOCK")
# where: dist_m = distance type used to calculate the pixel 11
# values' distance matrix
```

245

246 We applied the code written in Box 2, using a moving window of 9x9
247 pixels, to both: (i) the Similaun glacier upper area, mainly covered by alpine
248 conifer woodlands (dominated by *Picea abies*, *Larix decidua*, *Abies Alba*) and
249 rocks, as well as (ii) to the valley bottom (Val Venosta), a human-dominated
250 landscape devoted to agricultural areas and small urban villages.

251 Concerning the Similaun glacier area, the Shannon index showed medium
252 to high values everywhere, including areas with almost homogeneous rock
253 cover (i.e. alpine habitat) as well as areas with homogeneous tree cover
254 (i.e. coniferous forest habitat) (Figure 2). This is due to the fact that
255 Shannon's H does not take into account the distance among pixel values
256 but only the relative abundance of each value within the moving window
257 of 9x9 pixels. In this case, NDVI values showed subtle differences among
258 each others, especially in homogeneous areas and even when rescaled at 8 bit
259 (namely 256 possible integer values).

260 Low heterogeneity values were found in areas with snow cover; in that
261 case, the values of the neighboring pixels are so similar that they lead to a
262 low Shannon's H for the focal pixel centered on the moving window. The
263 saturation of high values of heterogeneity was apparent when considering
264 Rényi's entropy at low alpha values (Equation 2). This is related to the
265 aforementioned (see section '2.2 Rényi generalized entropy') negative expo-
266 nential curve relating the value of this index with respect to alpha, shown in
267 Ricotta et al. (2003a). The result is a map with saturated values of hetero-

268 geneity. This effect is softening when increasing the alpha parameter. The
269 **rasterdiv** package allows accounting for several indices at a time to avoid
270 heterogeneity saturation effects, for instance by considering distance among
271 pixel values besides relative abundance of each value. More specifically, run-
272 ning the Rao's Q function coded in **rasterdiv** allows to circumvent this issue
273 of saturated values of heterogeneity (refer to the bottom line of Figure 2). In
274 the Similaun glacier area, the homogeneous cover of spruce forests is better
275 reflected by the Rao's Q index as it better contrasts against the geological
276 heterogeneity of the upper alpine belt. Maximum Rao's Q values were found
277 at the interface between water (i.e. alpine lakes) and the surrounding vegeta-
278 tion and rocks, representing an interesting ecotone area (see the upper right
279 corner of the last panel in Figure 2).

280 The **rasterdiv** package, thanks to a combination of functions rooted in
281 Information Theory, thus helps to reveal hidden spatial patterns of hetero-
282 geneity, and allows measuring ecosystem heterogeneity related to both biotic
283 and abiotic components. By doing so, the **rasterdiv** package better discrimi-
284 nates among ecosystem features and functions constituting the landscape.

285 In the valley area (Val Venosta), this phenomenon was even more pro-
286 nounced (Figure 3) due to the higher spatial heterogeneity of the landscape
287 matrix under study with patches of small agricultural fields mixed with wa-
288 ter bodies (e.g., the Adige river in the middle of the valley), resulting in
289 very high values for both Rényi (alpha=0) and Shannon indices. Low to
290 medium values on the north- and south-facing slopes, indicate grasslands
291 and broadleaf forests. Again, the Rao's Q index helped to better discrimi-
292 nate among these areas and among different land uses. Indeed, by relying
293 on the relative numerical distance among the 8bit-NDVI pixel values, it can
294 differentiate between areas with low to medium heterogeneity values (blue
295 and light blue colors in Figure 3), i.e. grasslands and broadleaf forests, and
296 areas with medium to high heterogeneity values, i.e. upper mountain rocks
297 at the interface with the treeline and with alpine lakes, as well as riparian
298 vegetation besides the Adige river in the lower part of the valley.

299 With this study case focusing on a very heterogeneous area in the Alps,
300 we illustrated two main critical components of the **rasterdiv** package: (i)
301 how it allows to measure multiple indices simultaneously, and (ii) how it can
302 help detecting otherwise hidden patterns of heterogeneity in the landscape.

303 For the sake of clarity and to avoid a catalogue-like article, we did not
304 present all the indices that can be calculated by the **rasterdiv** package.
305 Instead, we decided to showcase a few, to illustrate to ecologists the high
306 potential of the **rasterdiv** package for applications in landscape ecology,
307 macroecology, biogeography and the analysis of spatiotemporal dynamics in
308 general. We refer to the manual of the package (<https://cran.r-project>).

309 [org/web/packages/rasterdiv/index.html](https://rasterdiv.org/web/packages/rasterdiv/index.html)) and its vignettes to find addi-
310 tional metrics and examples related to the package.

311 4 Discussion

312 In this paper, we provide an ecological overview of new R package `rasterdiv`.
313 The overarching rationale for proposing this new R package is to present a
314 set of methods and ready-to-use functions for calculating landscape hetero-
315 geneity metrics from space (e.g. satellite images), as well as from airborne
316 or ground-based devices, to monitor and analyze, among other things, bio-
317 diversity change, habitat fragmentation and land use and cover changes.

318 The importance of computing continuous spectral heterogeneity measures
319 from satellite-borne or airborne sensors to better discriminate among the
320 various components in the landscape has been highlighted in several studies
321 (Karlson et al., 2015; Godinho et al., 2018; Ribeiro et al., 2019; Doxa et al.,
322 2020). Nevertheless, caution is recommended when making use of continuous
323 remotely sensed data, and the radiometry of pixel values should be carefully
324 considered before applying such measures. For instance, relying on float
325 (decimal) precision data such as the NDVI (which ranges from -1 to 1), may
326 lead to a high neighboring heterogeneity which could actually be the effect
327 of data binning rather than the effect of an ecological underlying pattern. In
328 general, an 8-bit image (and therefore composed of 256 integer values/classes)
329 is preferable when applying spectral heterogeneity measures. In this paper,
330 we used an 8-bit NDVI layer rescaled from Copernicus data. However, one
331 might even rely on a multispectral system reduced to a single 8-bit layer
332 through by means of the first component of a Principal Component Analysis
333 or any multidimensionality reduction technique (Féret and Boissieu, 2020).

334 Most of metrics based on Information Theory can accommodate only one
335 layer at a time when relying on indices using abundance information only (in
336 the shown example, the Rényi entropy index and Shannon's H). However, the
337 `rasterdiv` package includes accounting for pixel values distances, such as the
338 Rao's Q index, which can integrate multiple layers of ecological information
339 such as multiple bands of satellite images or physical and biotic data (e.g.,
340 vegetation cover, soil pH, topography).

341 In general, remotely sensed data are simplifications of more complex sys-
342 tems depending on the radiometric and spectral properties of one or more
343 images. From an ecological point of view, the spectral space of an image
344 might be associated with the Hutchinson's hypervolume which orders geo-
345 metrically the variables shaping species' ecological niches (Hutchinson, 1959;
346 Blonder, 2018). Hence, calculating heterogeneity in such a space could pro-

347 vide important information about species niches variability or at least on the
348 landscape variability shaping species distribution (Rocchini et al., 2018).

349 Future local and global changes are expected to impact ecosystem hetero-
350 geneity. Since remotely sensed data nowadays allows us to rely on relatively
351 long and standardized time series, applying different measures of heterogene-
352 ity to multi-temporal stacks would enhance the power to estimate and po-
353 tentially forecast ecosystem heterogeneity shifts in space and time. This will
354 be an invaluable tool to allow targeted and efficient monitoring and planning
355 practices. For instance, due to the unprecedented rate of climate change, the
356 adaptation of species to climate change is a benchmark in ecology (Stein et
357 al., 2014). The `rasterdiv` package might also be particularly useful when
358 aiming at calculating climate-related heterogeneity, which is likely to shape
359 ecosystem heterogeneity patterns that species have adapted to. This could
360 be directly done running the functions on remotely sensed climate data (Metz
361 et al., 2014; Senner et al., 2018; Zellweger et al., 2019), which are expected
362 to drive several ecological functions at different spatial scales.

363 5 Conclusion

364 Measuring heterogeneity from space to understand ecological patterns and
365 processes acting across the landscape and over different time periods is cru-
366 cial to guide effective management practices, especially in the Anthropocene
367 epoch, in which human intervention is leading to rapid environmental changes
368 (Randin et al., 2020).

369 The proposed `rasterdiv` package is a powerful tool for monitoring spa-
370 tial and temporal variation of ecosystems' properties (Rocchini et al., 2018),
371 given the intrinsic relationship (*sensu* Laliberté et al., 2019) between the spa-
372 tial variation of ecosystems and that of the spectral signal from pixel values
373 (Rocchini et al., 2019). No single measure can provide a full description of all
374 the different aspects of ecosystem heterogeneity. That is why the `rasterdiv`
375 package offers multiple approaches to disentangle the complexity of ecosys-
376 tem heterogeneity in space and time through calculations deeply rooted in
377 Information Theory and based on reproducible Free and Open Source algo-
378 rithms.

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389 Authors’ contribution to the manuscript

390 DR, MI, ET, MM, DDR, EM, CT, SV contributed to the development of the
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393 DP, CR, MR, FS, MJS, MS, LS, PS, AKS, SS, ET, PZ, MW contributed to
394 the conceptual development of the theoretical background of the `rasterdiv`
395 package.

396 All authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

397 Data accessibility

Free data for applying the proposed functions are available directly into the
`rasterdiv` package (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv>). The
Copernicus Sentinel-2 image used in this paper can be freely downloaded
from: <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>, image tile reference:
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Figure 1: The Ötzi area in the northern Italian Alps, used for building an ecological example of the application of the `rasterdiv` package starting from a Copernicus Sentinel-2 image, represented by an RGB space in natural (red, green, blue) and false (near infrared, red, green) colors. Coordinates are in the UTM (WGS84, zone 32N) reference system.

Figure 2: The first row of the figure represents the area under study, namely the Similaun glacier as a subset of the study area in Figure 1. NDVI is shown in the natural range but it was rescaled to 8-bit before heterogeneity computation. Then, different metrics were applied: the Rényi's entropy index, the Shannon's H (corresponding to the Rényi's entropy with $\alpha = 1$), and the Rao's Q . Coordinates are in the UTM (WGS84, zone 32N) reference system.

Figure 3: The first row of the figure represents the area under study, namely the Val Venosta, a subset at a lower elevation with respect to the Similaun glacier of Figure 2, and thus with higher human impact. NDVI is shown in the natural range but it was rescaled to 8-bit before heterogeneity computation. Then, different metrics were applied: the Rényi's entropy, the Shannon's H (corresponding to the Rényi's entropy with $\alpha = 1$), and the Rao's Q . Coordinates are in the UTM (WGS84, zone 32N) reference system.

554 **Box 1 - Description of the moving window**
555 **approach**

556 Given a raster layer, ecologists usually split it into small chunks, called
557 moving windows. To estimate the value of the previously presented indices,
558 we first select l an odd number, which will correspond to the length of the
559 squared window. With this choice, we have a central entry in the window,
560 i.e. the $(\frac{l+1}{2}, \frac{l+1}{2})$ entry, which will be placed as a mask, in position $(1, 1)$
561 over our raster. The index is therefore computed only with the values which
562 the window covers. Notice that with this choice we will have some missing
563 values, which will not contribute in the index computation. The obtained
564 index value is stored in position $(1, 1)$ in the output raster. The following
565 step is moving the window so that its central entry is over the entry $(1, 2)$
566 of the raster. The index value computed is stored in the corresponding
567 position of the output raster, i.e. in $(1, 2)$. We proceed in this way until
568 the last entry of output raster is filled. This technique, visually presented
569 in Figure 4, is extremely popular in ecology since it is quite simple, robust
570 and powerful to simulate a biological boundary. Note that this technique
571 of computing index has a suitable algorithmic structure.

572 **Input:** a raster $R \in^{m \times n}$ (*Rényi*)
573 **Input:** an index computation function f
574 **Input:** an odd number l
575 **Output:** the raster with the index values OR
576 $m \in^{l \times l}$ (*Rényi*) is the moving window;
577 **for** $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ **do**
 for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ **do**
 we assign to m the values of R covered by a l side square mask at
 the step (i, j) ;
 f computes the index value with values covered by the moving win-
 dow m ;
 $OR_{ij} \leftarrow f(m)$;
 end
578 **end**

Figure 4: The moving window technique for the computation of diversity indices in the `rasterdiv` package, redrawn from Rocchini et al. (2013).